

CONSTRUCT CONSISTENCY IN THE ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS-RELATED BELIEFS: A THREE-WAY CROSS-SECTIONAL PILOT COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract. This paper reports on a comparative study of the mathematics-related beliefs of students in England, Slovakia and Spain. We draw on earlier work of the fourth author and his colleagues at the University of Leuven and the mathematics-related beliefs questionnaire (MRBQ) developed and trialled for use in Flanders. The original instrument, which was developed as a comprehensive and warranted measure of learner beliefs, yielded four factors predicted by the literature, although only two achieved satisfactory levels of reliability. The instrument was revised at the University of Cambridge and an analysis of data derived from students in England and Spain yielded four reliable factors. The conceptual structures of these factors not only matched closely those derived in the Belgian trials but also offered evidence to support a conjecture that students' mathematics-related beliefs have a cross-national structural equivalence. Consequently, the country sample was expanded to include students from Slovakia. In this paper we report on the findings derived from the three country analysis. Factor and multivariate analytic approaches were applied to the data. The former tended to confirm earlier findings that the instrument was comprehensive in its identification of the belief structures of students of mathematics and that these structures were consistent across countries. The latter highlighted the extent to which variation in the strengths with which beliefs are held are influenced by age, gender and nationality.

Key words: affects, attitudes towards mathematics, mathematics self-beliefs, usefulness of mathematics, achievements

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper we present an adaptation of the mathematics-related beliefs questionnaire (MRBQ) developed at the University of Leuven, Belgium (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003). The original team's intention was to develop, from

a warranted theoretical perspective, a comprehensive instrument for the assessment of students' beliefs about mathematics, its teaching and learning. The MRBQ was developed for use with Flemish students and showed itself sensitive to differences in the beliefs of students in different types of school and student gender (De Corte and Op 't Eynde, 2003; Op 't Eynde et al, 2006). However, several writers, particularly those in collaboration with Patricia Alexander (Alexander and Dochy, 1995; Alexander et al, 1998, Buehl and Alexander, 2006) have argued that, since evidence suggests "that culture played an important role in forming individuals' perceptions about knowledge and beliefs" (Alexander et al, 1998: 98), greater attention should be paid to beliefs research in different cultural contexts, not least since western conceptualisations may be inappropriate in non-western cultures (Chan and Elliott, 2004). Indeed, research has shown substantial variation in the belief structures, at least in respect of the nature of mathematics and mathematics teaching, between teachers from two diverse European cultures (Andrews and Hatch, 2000; Andrews, 2007a) and provides a further warrant for interest in this regard.

Importantly, the cultural transferability of the MRBQ has yet to be tested. Moreover, two of the four scales yielded by the original factor analyses achieved only moderate levels of reliability. In this paper reports we report on a refinement of the MRBQ and evaluate the revised instrument's transferability to different contexts and its sensitivity to age and gender. This involved gathering data from students in three culturally different European countries (England, Slovakia and Spain) at two ages (12 and 15). Thus, in some respects, our study can be construed as a replication study. Importantly, replication in other cultural settings, which are rarely undertaken (Bauman and Del Rio, 2005), can facilitate interpretability and allow "researchers to make comparisons about phenomena or issues in order to examine similarities and differences among the settings" (Bauman and Del Rio, 2005: 433).

2 FRAMING THE STUDY

Over the last few years researchers have to come to understand that cognition and metacognition are necessary but not sufficient psychological functions for effective learning and that affective factors are "important constituent elements of learning" (Op 't Eynde et al., 2002; 14). Indeed, Kilpatrick et al. (2001) have argued that mathematical proficiency comprises five intertwined strands of which one, productive disposition, refers to affective rather than cognitive or metacognitive interactions with the subject and embraces beliefs about mathematics, notions of self-efficacy, motivation to study, attitudes towards study and so on. Such findings resonate with De Corte et al.'s (2000) suggestion that a mathematical disposition comprises five similar qualities of

which one, mathematically-related beliefs, addresses the learner's subjective conceptions about mathematics education and beliefs about the self both as mathematician and member of the class, school and wider community. In short, there is a growing awareness that affective factors have a significant impact on all aspects of mathematical learning. Significantly, learner affect is influenced by a variety of factors including the context in which the learner lives and is schooled, the role of the teacher, and the day-to-day classroom interactions influenced by, for example, the learner's motivation (Kloosterman, 1988), self-confidence (Middleton and Spanias, 1999), effort (Kloosterman and Stage, 1992), self-efficacy (Schwarzer, 1992) and task value perceptions (Pintrich and De Groot, 1990).

Acknowledging these issues, the Leuven team developed the mathematics-related beliefs questionnaire (MRBQ) with the objective of categorising "the structure of belief systems and on an identification of the relevant categories of beliefs and the way they relate to each other" (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003; 3). In their review of the literature, Op 't Eynde et al. (2002) identified four categories of belief-related research which informed the development of their instrument. These were beliefs about the nature of mathematics and mathematical learning, beliefs about the self in the context of mathematical learning, beliefs about mathematics teaching and the social context of learning, and beliefs about the nature of knowledge and knowing. In so doing, they were attempting to reconcile the work of researchers in cognitive, motivational and affective research traditions who frequently "operate in relative isolation from each other" (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003; 3).

It is important, in framing this paper, to explicate our perspective on beliefs which, in the mathematics education literature, has proved to be a problematic area (Barkatas and Malone, 2005; McLeod and McLeod, 2002; Op 't Eynde et al., 2002), despite Pajares's (1992: 308) assertion that it "will not be possible for researchers to come to grips with teachers' beliefs without first deciding what they wish belief to mean and how this meaning will differ from that of similar constructs". Reasons for studying beliefs are well known and probably not in need of much rehearsal here. Sadly, despite this clear need to examine them, there remains no agreed definition of belief among mathematics-oriented researchers (McLeod and McLeod, 2002; Beswick, 2005, 2007). Aguirre and Speer (2000: 328), for example define beliefs "as personal philosophies (often implicitly held) consisting of conceptions, values and ideologies". Handal (2003) began his paper with the following definition; "For the purpose of this paper, teachers' mathematical beliefs refers to those belief systems held by teachers on the teaching and learning of mathematics", while Beswick (2005, 2007) construed beliefs as "anything that an individual regards as true". All three definitions are problematic. Aguirre and Speer define the term in relation to other constructs which they fail to define, Handal's definition is circular and

Beswick's is unsatisfactory not least because people hold beliefs, such as in the existence of a spiritual world beyond the tangible, which they know are unverifiable and accept as belief rather than knowledge. So, what sense can we make of the diverse literature on the topic, particularly in respect of other, similar, constructs and, importantly, knowledge?

McLeod (1992: 579), in acknowledging the problem, located beliefs, attitudes and emotions on several continua, writing that we can construe "beliefs, attitudes and emotions as representing increasing levels of affective involvement, decreasing levels of cognitive involvement, increasing levels of intensity of response, and decreasing levels of response stability". However, others have circumvented the discussion by ignoring. The former seems common, but not exclusively so, in research undertaken under the umbrella of psychology as reflected in, for example, Bauman and Del Rio (2005), Bråten and Strømsø (2005), Torff and Warburton (2005) and Valanides and Angeli (2005), all papers examining aspects of beliefs in different educational psychology journals.

In general, beliefs are thought to operate at two levels (Green, 1971, Abelson, 1979). At the lower level are single beliefs characterised in four ways; they may pertain to the existence of entities outside the believer's control, represent an idealistic alternative world, have both affective and evaluative components, and derive from a person's experiences (Abelson, 1979; Nespor, 1987). They are "deeply personal, rather than universal, and unaffected by persuasion. They can be formed by chance, experience, or a succession of events" (Pajares, 1992: 309). At the second level can be found belief systems which may be held in isolation of other belief systems, making the holding of conflicting beliefs possible (Green, 1971). Beliefs are filters through which experiences are interpreted (Pajares, 1992) and tools with which humans protect and promote themselves (Snow et al., 1996). However, more recent work has suggested that students' beliefs are complex, multidimensional, interactive, sociocultural, contextual, and developmental" (Buehl and Alexander, 2006: 39). Both time and experience are influential factors not only in the construction of beliefs but also the strength with which they are incorporated into existing structures (Baxter Magolda, 2004; Kuhn et al., 2000).

In respect of beliefs and knowledge, although Pehkonen and Pietilä (2003) argue the distinction is fuzzy, Abelson (1979) and Nespor (1987) suggest that beliefs are non-consensual and, consequently, disputable, while knowledge is generally verifiable. That is, beliefs "are distinguishable from knowledge only in terms of the degree of consensus they attract" (Beswick, 2005: 39) as they are individual constructs while knowledge is essentially socially constructed (Op 't Eynde et al. 2002). Indeed, Alexander et al (1998: 98) noted that knowledge is generally conceived by educational participants as "factual, proven information transmitted within the educational system" while beliefs were "more aligned with unproven but deeply held convictions that often arose from

life experiences". Furinghetti and Pehkonen (2002), in an attempt to clarify the situation, distinguish between objective and subjective knowledge as the formalised and collectively agreed knowledge that is mathematics and the individually constructed, experiential and tacit knowledge of the individual. The above findings have justified recent interest in intervention studies aimed at changing students' beliefs in line with Green's (1971) argument that teachers should minimise their students' subjective beliefs by attending to maximising their evidential beliefs.

In this paper we take beliefs to be "subjective, experienced-based, often implicit knowledge" (Pehkonen and Pietilä, 2003: 2), where, in particular, "students mathematics-related belief systems can be defined as the implicitly or explicitly held subjective conceptions students hold to be true about mathematics education, about themselves as mathematics learners, and about the mathematics class context" (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003: 4 (their emphasis)). In so doing, we accept the critical roles of knowledge and experience in belief formation. Importantly, such a definition allows for different interpretations of prior experience to lead to different people constructing different beliefs from similar experiences.

Research has indicated that beliefs, like motivation, attitude and other psychological constructs, are difficult to evaluate directly and are, essentially, accessible only by inference (Fenstermacher, 1978). In particular, while acknowledging that "our beliefs construct our experience, it is necessary to recognize that individually we may not be the best people to clearly enunciate our beliefs and perspectives since some of these may lurk beyond ready articulation" (Munby, 1982: 217). Such findings warrant the conviction that "the study of students' mathematics-related belief systems, more than the study of isolated beliefs, can push the field forward" (Op 't Eynde and De Corte 2003: 3). Conventionally beliefs have been examined by means of questionnaire surveys and exploratory factor analyses that enable researchers to determine the number and nature of the constructs that underlie a large number of items (De Vellis 1991). Importantly, since all variables correlate to some degree, the purpose of factor analyses "is to account for the intercorrelations among n variables, by postulating a set of common factors, considerably fewer in number than the number, n , of these variables" (Cureton and D'Agostino, 1983: 2). In relation to students' mathematics-related beliefs Op 't Eynde and De Corte (2003: 6) argued that a principal components analysis would "shed light ...concerning the question: Which categories and subcategories have empirical grounds?". Since this study is an attempt to develop further their work and incorporates a significant number of new or replacement items, our view was that confirmatory factor analyses would have been inappropriate.

In this paper we focus explicitly on the ways in which such beliefs are manifested in culturally different contexts. The majority of previous studies of

students' mathematics-related beliefs have been undertaken in single national contexts (Pintrich and De Groot, 1990) with few attempting explicit comparative evaluations. Indeed, Pehkonen, one of the foremost researchers in the field, has argued that "the international comparison of pupils' mathematical beliefs still seems to be an almost unexamined field" (Pehkonen, 1995: 34). This lack of attention to the comparative dimension is problematic and provocative of several pertinent questions. For example, does it mean that researchers working in one context assume that beliefs are so uniquely located in the context in which they were formed that cross-cultural transferability is impossible? Does it mean that researchers assume that domain-specific beliefs are held by all, irrespective of culture or context, with the consequence that any instrument valid in one context will be valid in another? Or does it mean that researchers have simply failed to consider the significance of national context? Such a failure, we believe, may be indicative of a rather naïve view on the subject. There is some evidence from studies undertaken in single cultural contexts that some beliefs are shared cross-culturally. For example, narrow beliefs like there is always a single routine to solve a mathematical problem, that mathematics is calculation or mathematics is the practising of rules have been identified in studies in the US (Garofalo, 1989a, 1989b; Spangler, 1992), Finland (Hannula et al, 1996; Pehkonen, 1992) and Hong Kong (Lam et al, 1999; Wong, 2002). However, the extent to which single common beliefs can be interpreted as reflecting cross-cultural beliefs systems remains questionable and provides further justification for our investigation.

As implied in the previous paragraph, of those studies that have examined students' beliefs comparatively – research in which Finnish students seem constantly implicated – the extent to which attempts have been made to uncover and explicate their structural properties have been variable. For example, Pehkonen and Tompa (1994), in a comparison of Finnish and Hungarian students' beliefs, used factor analyses to reduce large numbers of items to "compact" proportions before, essentially, ignoring the structural implications by attending to comparisons of individual items scores. In other studies researchers grouped items according to predetermined categorisation rather than systematic factor analyses, as in the case of Pehkonen's (1995) five way comparative study, Berry and Sahlberg's (1996) examination of Finnish and English students' beliefs and Graumann's (2001) study of German and Finnish students' mathematical views. Such studies, while helpful in framing what one does, are disappointing in their lack of attention to the structural aspects of beliefs.

The above studies indicate that comparative analyses of belief systems present a problematic enterprise and, we argue, the difficulties associated with the use in one system of an instrument derived in another are not difficult to understand. Osborn (2004) has argued that comparative researchers should attend, in particular, to issues of conceptual and linguistic equivalence in order to ensure that instruments measure what they are intended to measure. Indeed, the

problems of conceptual and linguistic equivalence go frequently unacknowledged in comparative research with the consequence that instruments effective in one culture are not in another – a problem experienced by Mason (2003) in her Italian adaptation of the Kloosterman and Stage (1992) instrument. Such problems, frequently a consequence of one country's researchers dominating a project's instrument development and protocols, have compromised much comparative mathematics education research (Keitel and Kilpatrick, 1999, Wiliam, 1998). However, overcoming such difficulties is time-consuming and expensive. Andrews (2007b), for example, describes how researchers, drawn from five European countries, spent a year exposing each others' culturally-located beliefs about the nature of effective teaching before being able to develop an agreed framework for describing mathematics classroom activity. In the light of such work it is not surprising that the importance of such negotiation is overlooked, particularly when considered against the conception underpinning large scale studies like TIMSS and PISA, of mathematics curricula congruence.

3 METHOD

The original study set out to categorise “the structure of belief systems and on an identification of the relevant categories of beliefs and the way they relate to each other” (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003; 3). The instrument developed yielded four factors in line with the theoretical perspectives adopted and reflected, unlike most other studies, the structural or systemic relationships between the underlying psychological constructs. However, only two of the four associated scales achieved satisfactory levels of reliability and no attempt has yet been made to determine the extent to which the instrument would prove successful in cultures other than the Flemish in which it was developed. Thus, our goal was to adapt and augment the original questionnaire to see if we could improve the reliability of the factor scales and determine the extent to which the revised instrument would evaluate students' mathematics-related beliefs in different cultural contexts.

The MRBQ comprised 58 items which were reduced to 40 by the original Leuven analyses. These were augmented by a further 33 drawn from various sources which we thought would not only supplement but improve the original scale. These sources included, inter alia, scales used by Kloosterman and Stage (1992) and Pintrich and De Groot (1990). All items were subjected to the scrutiny of several colleagues in both England and Spain in order to establish not only conceptual and linguistic equivalence (Osborn, 2004) but also to ensure that each was as concise as possible. This process was less straightforward than expected and reflected many of the problems of comparative work described by Andrews (2007b). The English and Spanish versions were piloted on a small number of

volunteer students and 73 items were finally reduced to 60. Finally, all the items were placed alongside a six point Likert scale and strategically mixed. A six point scale was used in accordance with the approach of the Leuven team and because we believed that forcing a decision would improve the quality of the data yielded. The revised questionnaire was administered in one school near Cambridge, England (220 students), three near Santander, Spain (405 students) and one in Bratislava, Slovakia (250 students). The data, from students at ages 11/12 and 14/15, chosen as representing transitional points of a child's schooling irrespective of location, were collected between the spring of 2006 and the summer of 2007. Importantly, since no statistical criteria for the selection of the sample have been applied, results cannot be generalised at a national level. They will however provide preliminary insights about the structure of student mathematics-related beliefs across the four culturally different samples.

4 RESULTS

The Leuven team undertook principal components with varimax rotation analysis which yielded a four factor solution. Consequently in accordance with the earlier work, a similar process, though with slight variation, was adopted. Firstly, a four factor solution was forced for each country's data. For the purposes of economy we do not report the details of those solutions although we believe that what follows will provide more than adequate compensation for the omission. Factors scores were then calculated for all students on each factor identified by each of the individual country analyses. Thus, each student had twelve factor scores allotted to him or her. Conventionally, according to Gorard (1997), individual factor scores are a summation of each individual item score multiplied by its factor loading. In this way, since the item loading is a measure of the correlation between the item and the underlying construct represented by the factor, each item's contribution to the factor score is proportional to the variance explained by that item. Therefore, at least in these initial stages, this is how factor scores were calculated. Correlations were then calculated to determine the extent to which factors defined by the analysis of one country reflected those of another. The outcomes of this process can be seen in table 1.

It can be seen from the figures of table 1 that the factors Slovakia 2, England 2 and Spain 1 were essentially equivalent. Their correlations, taken pairwise, were 0.970, 0.978 and 0.983 respectively which yielded a mean variance of 95.5 per cent. We can also see that the factors Slovakia 1, England 1 and Spain 3, with correlations 0.991, 0.959 and 0.976 respectively and a mean variance of 95.1 per cent, were also effectively the same. Also the factors Slovakia 3, England 3 and Spain 2, with correlations 0.931, 0.891 and 0.924 and mean variance 83.8 per cent were very close while, finally, the factors Slovakia 4, England 4 and Spain 4,

with correlations 0.858, 0.861 and 0.910 and a mean variance of 76.9 per cent were also close. These figures show that for each factor identified by one country's analysis there was an equivalent factor identified by each of the other countries analyses. Importantly, from the perspective of our project, these high levels of agreement warranted a decision to combine data from all three countries and undertake a new factor analysis. Again, in line with the original study, a four factor solution was forced. Details of the four factors, which accounted for 44.7 per cent of the variance and which compares favourably with the 38.3 of the original study, can be seen below and form the basis for what follows.

Table 1

Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on the full data set between the 12 factors yielded by the three country analyses

	Slov 1	Slov 2	Slov 3	Slov 4	Engl. 1	Engl 2	Engl 3	Engl 4
England 1	0.991	0.565	0.699	-0.378				
England 2	0.551	0.970	0.569	-0.310				
England 3	0.711	0.623	0.931	-0.373				
England 4	-0.322	-0.238	-0.316	0.858				
Spain 1	0.544	0.978	0.574	-0.380	0.527	0.983	0.564	-0.204
Spain 2	0.796	0.597	0.891	-0.349	0.755	0.563	0.924	-0.266
Spain 3	0.959	0.517	0.662	-0.362	0.976	0.491	0.647	-0.298
Spain 4	-0.184	-0.223	-0.195	0.861	-0.153	-0.121	-0.202	0.910

Below can be seen the items, with loadings, of the first factor yielded by the forced four factor solution deriving from the combined data set. The Cronbach alpha for this scale of 0.924 compared well with the original study's 0.921.

Table 2

Combined factor 1

Loading	Item
0.798	My teacher is friendly to us.
0.781	My teacher listens carefully to what we say.
0.778	My teacher understands our problems and difficulties with mathematics.
0.777	My teacher tries to make the mathematics lessons interesting.
0.772	My teacher appreciates it when we try hard, even if our results are not so good.
0.729	My teacher always shows us, step by step, how to solve a problem, before giving us exercises.
0.725	My teacher really wants us to enjoy learning new things.
0.689	My teacher always gives us time to explore new problems and try out different solution strategies.
0.659	My teacher wants us to understand the content of this mathematics course.

0.580	My teacher explains why mathematics is important.
0.561	My teacher thinks mistakes are okay as long as we are learning from them.
-0.486	My teacher is too absorbed in mathematics to notice us.
-0.433	My teacher does not really care how we feel in class.
0.408	We do a lot of group work in this mathematics class.

Every item in this factor, although some are slight variants of the items of the MRBQ, could be found in the first factor identified in the original analyses of the MRBQ. Our interpretation is that many of the items address the encouragement of a productive disposition towards mathematical learning as much as they do the learning itself. For example, a number of items, as indicated by words such as *enjoy*, *appreciates*, and *friendly* address the affective domain while others, as indicated by *understand*, *explore* and *explain*, seem focused explicitly on the cognitive. Op 't Eynde and De Corte (2003) concluded that the factor attended, in a rather generic sense, to students' beliefs about "the role and functioning of their own teacher" and we would not disagree with that, although we would tentatively suggest that it was more focused on the **teacher's role as facilitator of learning**. In this way notions of affect and cognition are accommodated. Interestingly, this dichotomous interpretation alludes to the possibility of sub-factors which the original study's theoretical model predicted.

Below can be seen the items, with loadings, of the second factor yielded by the forced four factor solution deriving from the combined data set. The alpha coefficient for this factor (0.927) was comparable with that of the original (0.89).

Table 3

Combined factor 2

Loading	Item
0.704	I understand everything we have done in mathematics this year.
0.693	I can understand even the most difficult topics taught me in mathematics.
0.677	I like doing mathematics.
0.673	Compared with others in the class, I think I'm good at mathematics.
0.654	I'm very interested in mathematics.
0.642	I think I will do well in mathematics this year.
0.610	I think that what I am learning in this class is interesting.
0.602	I expect to do well on the mathematics tests and assessments we do.
0.597	I can usually do mathematics problems that take a long time to complete.
0.593	I like what I am learning in this class.
0.587	I don't have to try too hard to understand mathematics.
0.570	I am certain I can learn how to solve the most difficult mathematics problem.
0.553	I find I can do hard mathematics problems with patience.

0.541	I prefer mathematics when I have to work hard to find a solution.
0.517	I prefer class work that is challenging so I can learn new things.
0.412	If I try hard enough I understand the mathematics we are taught.
0.409	I study mathematics because I know how useful it is.

The second factor seems focused on the student's perception of his or her ability to succeed with mathematics. The use of expressions such as *I understand*, *I expect* and *I am certain* all point towards some sense of mathematical self-efficacy while expressions like *I'm very interested*, *I like what I am learning* and *I think that what I am learning in this class is interesting* all allude to beliefs about the cognitive worth of mathematics. In this regard, the factor resonates closely with that of the second factor of the original analysis which was summarised as a factor concerned with task value and self-efficacy beliefs, which we summarise here as mathematical **competence**. As with the first factor, the dichotomous nature of the items alludes to possible sub-factors.

Below can be seen the items, with loadings, of the third factor yielded by the forced four factor solution deriving from the combined data set. The alpha coefficient obtained ($\alpha = 0.890$) was a substantial improvement on the 0.65 of the original study.

Table 4

Combined factor 3

Loading	Item
0.636	I think mathematics is an important subject.
0.609	Knowing mathematics will help me earn a living.
0.597	Mathematics is used all the time in people's daily life.
-0.597	Studying mathematics is a waste of time.
-0.580	Mathematics has no relevance to my life.
0.579	I study mathematics because I know how useful it is.
0.577	Mathematics is a worthwhile and necessary subject.
0.564	Mathematics enables us to better understand the world we live in
0.556	I think that what I am learning in this class is useful for me to know.
0.472	Time used to understand why a solution works is time well spent.
0.457	I can use what I learn in mathematics in other subjects.
0.430	I think it is important to learn different strategies for solving the same problem.
0.427	Routine exercises are very important in the learning of mathematics.
-0.404	Only the mathematics to be tested is worth learning.
0.402	I like what I am learning in this class.

The Leuven team's third factor was thought to relate to "the usefulness of mathematics in real life and, more general, to the fact that mathematics is

grounded in human practices and is perceived as a dynamic discipline” (Op 't Eynde and De Corte, 2003: 6). A number of the original items of this factor had been adapted for our study. However, a number of items like *mathematics is continuously evolving* and *new things are still discovered*, which were thought to refer to a “dynamic, socio-constructivist view of mathematics”, had been removed from our scale as they were thought to be inaccessible to Spanish and English audiences. Furthermore, several of the original items like *anyone can learn mathematics* and *there are several ways to find the correct solution of a mathematics problem*, which were thought by the Leuven team to be related to a socio-constructivist perspective on learning, had been removed at the pilot stage as they had not loaded on any factors. Thus, in summary, the majority of the items of our third factor appear focused on student perceptions of mathematical **relevance**. This can be construed in terms of successful participation in the real world, mathematics as an intrinsically worthwhile subject or mathematics as a service to other occupations. Clearly there is some resonance between this factor and the third factor of the original analysis, but view is that neither this, nor any of the other factors that emerged from our analysis, reflects the “social activity” dimension underpinning the third factor identified in the original MRBQ analysis. Mathematical relevance, as defined by the items of this factor, indicates the possibility of sub-factors, each of which may reflect a different component of relevance.

Below can be seen the items, with loadings, of the fourth factor yielded by the forced four factor solution deriving from the combined data set. The reliability coefficient for this last scale (0.777) was an improvement on the original (0.69).

Table 5

Combined factor 4

Loading	Item
0.610	Getting the right answer is more important than understanding why the answer works.
0.581	Only very intelligent students can understand mathematics.
0.553	Ordinary students cannot understand mathematics, but only memorise the rules they learn.
0.537	My teacher wants us just to memorise the content of this mathematics course.
0.504	If I can not solve a mathematics problem quickly, I quit trying.
0.497	Only the mathematics to be tested is worth learning.
0.491	If I can not do a mathematics problem in a few minutes, I probably can not do it at all.
0.460	By doing the best I can in mathematics I try to show my teacher that I'm better than other students.
0.450	My teacher does not really care how we feel in class.

0.446	Everybody has to think hard to solve a mathematics problem.
0.445	It's a waste of time when our teacher makes us think on our own.
0.435	There is only one way to find the correct solution to a mathematics problem.
0.431	My only interest in mathematics is getting a good grade.
0.422	Studying mathematics is a waste of time.
0.421	My teacher thinks she/he knows everything best.
0.419	Mathematics learning is mainly about having a good memory.

The fourth factor of the Leuven analysis, theoretically predicted as mathematics as a domain of excellence, comprised items like *by doing the best I can in mathematics I want to show the teacher I'm better than most of the other students*, which was perceived as reflecting “students’ extrinsic goal orientation beliefs”, and items like *there is only one way to find the correct answer on a mathematical problem*, which was thought to represent “an absolutist view of mathematical learning”. Overall, such items “deal with the importance to excel in mathematics” (Op ’t Eynde and De Corte, 2003: 6). Although, the original fourth factor and our fourth factor share many items, our view is that it reflects less a perspective on mathematics as a domain of excellence than it does mathematics as a difficult subject, which is essentially incomprehensible to all but an intellectual elite and which, for the majority, is rote learnt. Moreover, our interpretation is that the negative register of the majority of items is less suggestive of a domain of excellence – something to which learners might aspire – than a **functional necessity** of school life. As with the three factors above, the items of this final factor also indicate the possibility of sub-factors and this will be discussed below.

Table 6

Correlations calculated on the full data set between weighted factor scores and simple mean factor scores

	Weighted teacher's role		Weighted competence
Mean teacher's role	0.995	Mean competence	0.998
	Weighted relevance		Weighted necessity
Mean relevance	0.902	Mean necessity	0.988

5 EVALUATING THE REVISED MRBQ

The factor scores for these combined factors were calculated in the manner discussed above. Unfortunately, such scores tend not to reflect the dimensions of the scale used to gather the data and tend, unless standardised, to present individual scores which are difficult to interpret. Consequently, a second set of factor scores was calculated for all data. In this case the factor score for an individual was the mean of all that person's scores on all the items that loaded on the factor. This would give a score for each individual that was simpler to interpret. However, in order to be able to use these new factor scores with confidence it was important to determine the extent to which they could be construed as equivalent to the originals. To this end, correlations were calculated between the original, weighted, factor scores and the simple mean factor scores. The results can be seen in table 6. The magnitudes indicate quite clearly that the simple mean, allowing for ease of interpretation, can be used as a proxy for the true factor scores.

Finally, as a statistical form of back translation, and in order to confirm the validity of the simple factors as proxies for the individual country factors, correlations were calculated between the original country factors and the simple mean factors scores for each country's data in turn. In so doing, we were testing the extent to which the project factors represented, at the country level, individual county factors. The results of these correlations can be seen in table 7. The figures of table 7 show clearly that the correlations between each country's factors are sufficiently high to confirm their representing equivalent constructs. Indeed, the variance calculations show that very little is not explained by the correlations. Thus, when we talk about the English factor 2, we can relate this directly to the Slovakian factor 2 or the Spanish factor 1, to the extent that the combined factor 1, beliefs about the teacher's role as a facilitator of learning, can be seen to represent them all. Consequently, the following draws solely on analyses of the simple-to-interpret factor scores.

The figures below show Pearson correlation coefficients and associated variance calculated for the data of each country between that country's factors, as represented in a simple mean calculation and the combined sample's factors. No probabilities have been included as the correlations are of sufficient size as to make them redundant. For example, the largest probability associated with the values in the table is smaller than 10^{-72} . All other probabilities would have been smaller and allow us to reject, with effective certainty, any null hypothesis that the factors are uncorrelated.

Table 7

Pearson correlation coefficients and associated variance calculated for the data of each country between that country's factors, as represented in a simple mean calculation and the combined sample's factors.

	Slovakia 2	England 2	Spain 1	Mean variance
Mean teacher's role	0.988	0.959	0.972	
	97.6	92.0	94.5	94.7
	Slovakia 1	England 1	Spain 3	
Mean competence	0.984	0.991	0.979	
	96.8	98.2	95.8	97.0
	Slovakia 3	England 3	Spain 2	
Mean relevance	0.944	0.982	0.934	
	89.1	96.4	87.2	90.9
	Slovakia 4	England 4	Spain 4	
Mean necessity	0.858	0.926	0.979	
	73.6	85.7	95.8	85.1
Mean variance	89.3	93.1	93.4	

6 THE EFFECT OF AGE, GENDER AND NATIONALITY

Table 8

Mean factor scores and standard deviations for each country's data with t-tests comparing each country's mean with that of all others. A score of 3.5 represents neutrality.

	Spain		England		Slovakia		All	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Teacher's role	2.43 ¹	1.01	2.84 ⁵	0.98	2.66	0.99	2.60	1.01
Competence	2.66 ²	0.85	3.47 ⁶	0.90	3.30 ⁸	1.03	3.04	0.99
Relevance	2.51 ³	0.52	2.85 ⁷	0.57	2.90 ⁹	0.67	2.71	0.61
Necessity	4.34 ⁴	0.70	4.07	0.61	3.69 ¹⁰	0.60	4.09	0.71
	t	p	t	p	t	p	t	p
1	-4.627	<10 ⁻⁵	5	-4.199	<10 ⁻⁵	8	-4.980	<10 ⁻⁶
2	-11.775	<10 ⁻²⁹	6	-7.586	<10 ⁻¹³	9	-5.655	<10 ⁻⁷
3	-9.593	<10 ⁻²⁰	7	-4.212	<10 ⁻⁵	10	11.161	<10 ⁻²⁶
4	10.437	<10 ⁻²³						

In respect of nationality there are some obvious variations in factor scores. The figures of table 8 show that the Spanish scores were significantly more positive on all four factors (acknowledging the negative register of mathematics

as a functional necessity) than the scores of all other students. English students were significantly less positive (but were not negative) in respect of beliefs about their teachers' role, their competence and the relevance of mathematics than students elsewhere, although in terms of personal competence with mathematics, their scores were essentially neutral. Slovakian students were significantly less positive in terms of beliefs concerning competence, relevance and necessity than students elsewhere, with the latter also tending towards neutrality.

Table 9

Mean factor scores and standard deviations for each age and gender along with the results of comparative t-tests. A score of 3.5 represents neutrality.

	Age 14/15		Age 11/12		Female		Male	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Teacher's role	2.97 ¹	1.06	2.27 ¹	0.83	2.60	0.97	2.60	1.04
Competence	3.39 ²	0.99	2.74 ²	0.87	3.21 ⁵	0.98	2.89 ⁵	0.96
Relevance	2.96 ³	0.62	2.48 ³	0.51	2.74	0.60	2.67	0.62
Necessity	4.03 ⁴	0.67	4.14 ⁴	0.74	4.16 ⁶	0.67	4.02 ⁶	0.73
		t	p		t	p		
	1	10.729	0.000	4	2.180	0.029		
	2	10.297	0.000	5	4.983	0.000		
	3	12.409	0.000	6	2.780	0.006		

The figures of table 9 show that, on average, older students have less positive beliefs about mathematics and its teaching than younger students. However, neither group appeared negative in respect of any factor although the older students' mean competence score was very close to neutral. In terms of gender, both groups were essentially positive in their responses to each factor although females were significantly less positive than males in respect of their competence but significantly more positive in respect of their rejection of mathematics as a functional necessity. However, as the analyses of variance reported in table 10 show, caution should be exercised in interpreting such data as the combined effects of the background variables may offer more compelling explanations. To determine the extent to which any differences were significant, and to examine the combined influence of nationality, age and gender, analyses of variance were undertaken. The results of these, which can be seen in table 10, offer some interesting insights.

Firstly, there was no significant combined effect of all three variables on any of the four factors. Secondly, the pair-wise tests showed that age and gender had no combined influence on any factor. Thirdly, however, nationality, taken with either age or gender had significant combined effects on several factors.

Fourthly, as we have already seen, each of gender, nationality and age had some significant influences on several of the factors.

Looking at the combined effect of nationality and gender we can see from the figures of table 10 that all factors except beliefs about the relevance of mathematics are prone to a combined effect. To locate the source of these differences means were calculated for each influenced factor for each constituent group and are presented in table 11. In respect of beliefs about the teacher's role as a facilitator of learning, English female students were the least positive of all six groups while Spanish females were the most positive. Slovak students, irrespective of gender, fell somewhere in the middle while English males were marginally less positive than the average and Spanish males marginally more positive than the average. Overall, though, it is probably true to say that the project level means of males and females, which were seen in table 9 to be equal, were a consequence of little variation between males (0.26 of a point) but much more between females (0.57 of a point).

Table 10

Results of analyses of variance undertaken to determine the influence both singly and multiply of student age, gender and nationality of factor scores

	Teacher's role		Competence		Relevance		Necessity	
	F	p	F	p	F	p	F	p
Gender (G)	0.08	0.771	23.35	0.000	0.70	0.402	7.42	0.007
Age (A)	102.01	0.000	107.95	0.000	148.47	0.000	2.71	0.100
Nationality (N)	11.96	0.000	66.03	0.000	40.27	0.000	81.71	0.000
G x A	1.79	0.181	3.71	0.054	1.08	0.298	1.37	0.242
G x N	4.56	0.011	4.13	0.016	0.15	0.857	6.36	0.002
A x N	4.75	0.009	5.29	0.005	3.75	0.024	4.16	0.016
G x A x N	2.75	0.064	1.40	0.248	0.04	0.958	0.71	0.491

In respect of beliefs about personal competence with mathematics, the figures of table 11 show that Spanish males were the most positive group with English females slipping into the negative. Across all three countries, however, the males were more positive than the females. Thus, the project level means, where the female was significantly less positive than the male, can be explained. Lastly, in terms of mathematics as a functional necessity Spanish females were the most positive in their rejection while Slovakian males, essentially neutral, the least positive. Also, the English scores were essentially the same, at around the project level mean, with Spanish males less positive in their rejection but Slovak males more positive in their rejection. Thus, again, the mean scores can be explained.

Table 11

Means and standard deviations calculated for each factor identified as prone to the combined influence of nationality and gender

		Female		Male	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Teacher's role	Spain	2.37	0.89	2.48	1.09
	Slovakia	2.61	0.93	2.70	1.06
	England	2.94	1.04	2.74	0.90
Competence	Spain	2.77	0.83	2.56	0.85
	Slovakia	3.38	0.97	3.22	1.10
	England	3.71	0.93	3.21	0.78
Necessity	Slovakia	3.75	0.57	3.63	0.63
	England	4.05	0.60	4.09	0.62
	Spain	4.51	0.60	4.21	0.75

In terms of the combined impact of nationality and age the figures of table 12 present an interesting story. For example, in terms of beliefs about the teacher's role as a facilitator of learning, Spanish students at age 12 were the most positive while English students at age 15 were the least positive. Younger students were always more positive than older, irrespective of nationality.

Table 12

Mean and standard deviations by nationality and age for each of the factors identified by the analyses of variance as prone to a combined influence

		Age 15		Age 12	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Teacher's role	Spain	2.91	1.11	2.07	0.73
	Slovakia	2.98	1.03	2.21	0.74
	England	3.04	1.03	2.69	0.91
Competence	Spain	3.00	0.88	2.39	0.72
	England	3.66	0.95	3.32	0.82
	Slovakia	3.68	0.98	2.79	0.87
Relevance	Spain	2.73	0.52	2.34	0.46
	England	3.07	0.59	2.69	0.50
	Slovakia	3.16	0.65	2.55	0.51
Necessity	Spain	4.37	0.60	4.32	0.77
	England	3.92	0.62	4.18	0.58
	Slovakia	3.70	0.58	3.68	0.64

From the perspective of student beliefs about personal mathematical competence, the data suggest that the older English and Slovak students were essentially neutral in their beliefs while the young Spanish students were particularly positive. However, while the younger English students were only marginally less positive than their older compatriots (a difference of 0.34 points), the younger Slovak students differed considerably from theirs (a difference of 0.89 points).

In respect of beliefs about the relevance of mathematics young Spanish students were the most positive and older Slovak students the least. Moreover, younger students from each country were more positive than their older colleagues by roughly 0.4 of a point. Lastly, in terms of mathematics as a functional necessity, the data show that Spanish students, irrespective of age were the most positive in their rejection while Slovakian, also irrespective of age, were the least positive. The English students' scores fell between the two with, interestingly, the older students' scores being significantly less positive than the younger.

7 DISCUSSION

The four factors of our analysis share much in common with those derived from the Leuven analysis. There are some differences, partly due to the removal of some items and the incorporation of others, but overall the underlying constructs are remarkably similar. This is encouraging as it provides evidence of the robustness of the original instrument and the quality of its theoretical underpinning. Importantly, it shows that elements of students' mathematics-related belief systems appear to transcend European cultural boundaries at least across the four national samples selected. Whether the same or similar constructs would be found in non-European cultures will require further study, although recent research highlighting the influence of Socratic and Confucian philosophies on culturally West and culturally Chinese educational traditions (Leung, 2001; Tweed & Lehman, 2002; Watkins, 2000) would suggest more by way of difference than similarity. It is interesting to note, however, that even within the European context; the construct similarity discussed above belies substantial cultural influences on the construction of different educational traditions. Sharpe (1997), for example, notes how the Protestant and Roman Catholic churches have shaped the development of education in England and France. Osborn (2004) discusses how societal emphases on the progress of the individual, community and nation have informed educational practices and expectations in England, Denmark and France respectively. In respect of mathematics, Kaiser (1999) reports how societal differences in the philosophical underpinnings of the English and German educational systems have influenced the presentation of mathematics to students, while Andrews (2007a), in contrast to Le Tendre et al's (2001) assertion of belief similarity, found substantial variation in English and Hungarian teachers' espoused

beliefs about mathematics and its teaching. Such cross-cultural variation makes the similarity of belief structures all the more remarkable and implies, although further research will be needed, that students' mathematics-related belief systems share much in common irrespective of cultural location.

It is clear from the above that despite the structural similarities the intensity with which beliefs are held is prone to a number of influencing variables. It is probably not surprising that students' beliefs about all aspects of mathematics and its teaching become less positive as they grow older. Indeed, this is a not unexpected outcome and can be construed as additional validation of the instrument's authority, particularly in the light of this age-related decline occurring in all three countries. It is probably not surprising that each of the four factors was prone to the influence of nationality in highly significant ways. It is also not surprising that gender was an influence on two of the factors. Indeed, the significantly higher scores of boys on mathematical competence and less negative in respect of the functional necessity of mathematics reflected similar findings of the original study (De Corte and Op 't Eynde: 2003).

However, the complex combined effect of nationality and age on each of the four factors indicated that the interplay of such variables remains difficult to characterise and may camouflage underlying structural differences which the current instrument may lack the sensitivity to access. This sense of interactive complexity was identified by the Leuven team when it attempted to examine the interplay of gender, track level¹ and student achievement on Flemish students' mathematics related beliefs (De Corte and Op 't Eynde, 2003). Some of their findings were as expected; for example, students in higher tracks tended to hold more positive beliefs than those in lower tracks, high achieving students were more positive than lower achieving students in respect of the relevance of mathematics, while boys were more positive than girls in respect of mathematics as a domain of excellence. Significantly, from the perspective of our interpretation of our data, the unequivocal influence of track level "certainly substantiates the influence of the social context on students' belief systems" as it "can be interpreted as a composite variable that includes a variety of classroom and other characteristics" De Corte and Op 't Eynde (2003:5). In respect of our study, nationality can be construed in similar fashion to track level as all the variables the Leuven team associated with track level – "the actual content of the mathematics classes,... the teaching style, class grouping, disciplinary problems, parents' expectations, etc" – are likely to differentiate between educational systems more

¹ In respect of Flemish education, students elect to join one of three tracks. These are classically-oriented and include courses in Latin and Greek, humanities-oriented, and vocationally-oriented. The core curriculum, including mathematics, for each track is the same although track choice is frequently linked to perceptions of ability and parental and student expectations of the educational system. Thus, there is a selection process implicit within the rhetoric of choice.

than within them. However, as with our study, the combined effect of tracking and gender, and achievement and gender indicated far from simple interactions.

Clearly the study of beliefs remains a problematic endeavour. This study, drawing on the earlier work of the Leuven team, has identified a number of belief systems about mathematics, its teaching and learning and shown clearly the influence of context on their formation. However, despite the Leuven team's ambition to construct a comprehensive instrument, much remains to be done. For example, Ruthven and Coe's (1994) study of epistemological beliefs identified six constructs of which three, *receptive preference*, *uncritical factualism* and *constrained factualism* accord with elements of mathematics as a functional necessity. However, we are conscious that the first of their factors, *proof certitude*, which addressed beliefs about the role of proof in the generation of mathematical knowledge, is missing from our instrument and presents an area for further development. This interest is further warranted by studies of high schools students' beliefs about mathematical ways of knowing. Both Gfeller et al (2000) and Coe and Ruthven (1994), in separate investigations of high-school students' beliefs about mathematical ways of knowing within *reform-oriented* curricula, found that the "most common misconception expressed by the students was the idea that mathematical knowledge is justified only through observation of physical phenomena" (Gfeller et al, 2000: 19) to the extent that "students' proof strategies were primarily and predominantly empirical, with a very low incidence of strategies that could be described as deductive" (Coe and Ruthven, 1994: 52). The two studies' conjectured explanations differed. The former suggested that "increased attention to real-world problems... may mislead students to thinking that mathematics must be linked to the real-world", thus providing "an incomplete picture of how mathematical knowledge is justified" (Gfeller et al, 2000: 19/20). The second argued that teachers' use of "prototypical examples of investigative tasks, and standardising templates for their conduct and reporting" have colluded in making the "process of enquiry more teachable and testable" and, in so doing, not only subverted curricula intentions but promoted "the continuing triumph of a hidden curriculum over the rhetoric of reform" (Coe and Ruthven, 1994: 52). In short, it seems clear not only is the revised MRBQ in need of further development but also, that beliefs about mathematics and the means by which knowledge is generated are highly contextualised. Accounting for such differences, particularly in the light of what we know about the mathematics curricula of different countries, will be an exciting venture.

Another area for further work concerns the identification and analysis of any sub-factors. We indicated above that variation in the items of each of the four factors alluded to possibilities in this regard and the conceptualisation of the original study implied an expectation of their existence. However, the Leuven team did not undertake such a secondary analysis and although reporting details is beyond this paper, our own secondary analyses of the four individual

scales, at the level of each country's data, indicated that there are both common and unique sub-factors. For example, the items of the factor competence with mathematics, when subjected to a secondary analysis, yielded two sub-factors which appeared robust and reliable. The first seemed concerned with a student perception of enjoyment in the intellectual demands of mathematics or mathematics as pleasurable and demanding. The second, which was not unrelated to the first, related to a sense of absolute mathematical competence. However, these analyses are at an early stage and beyond the scope of this paper.

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